

GO-BC Technical Blue Carbon Workshop, Gujarat, India

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Foreword

In January 2024, the United Nations Ocean Decade Programme for Blue Carbon (GO-BC), in partnership with Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology (GUIDE) and the Global Centre for Environment and Energy, Ahmedabad University hosted a workshop (24-25 January) at Ahmedabad University. Our objectives were to strengthen the international partnership opportunities for the growing interest in blue carbon research across India and to help mobilize the blue carbon community's engagement with the UN Ocean Decade. Our workshop was supported by the UK Government through grant funding to GO-BC via the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA).

Prior to the workshop itself, a group of scientists from GO-BC, including representatives from our executive committee and science technical working group, joined colleagues from GUIDE, DEFRA, Ahmedabad University, and the Global Mangrove Alliance to visit mangrove restoration sites in the Kachchh district of Gujarat. This fact-finding tour included sites visits, engagement with the local community and stakeholders, a school visit, and a meeting with the Adani Foundation, who have supported several compensatory habitat projects in the region of Mundra Port, which is operated by the Adani Group.

As well as the excellent presentations and scientific discussions of the workshop itself, a priority research question exercise was conducted and is currently being refined and written-up for publication (*Priority setting of India's Blue Carbon ecosystems as Nature-based solutions for Climate, People and Biodiversity*). We anticipate that scientific discussion, including considerations of socio-economic factors and policy opportunities, will help further support and strengthen India's national engagement with blue carbon policy levers, including scope for implementation of blue carbon habitats into India's nationally determined contributions (NDCs). NDCs can include blue carbon commitments and actions as part of the global stocktake within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), and with the next global stocktake due in 2025, we hope that our blue carbon workshop and this reporting will support these ambitions in India and help inspire others in the wider region.

William Austin, Vijay Kumar, and Minal Pathak

Photo: Workshop participants from the GO-BC Blue Carbon workshop, Gujarat, India.

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Meeting summary

Day 1 – Mangrove field site visits

On the first day of field visits, external experts from the GO-BC science technical working group visited Mundra and Luni mangrove field sites, led by colleagues from the Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology. Visiting researchers were joined by representatives from the local community and the Adani group, to gain insights into how local communities and businesses are involved with mangrove restoration projects in the Kachchh region of Gujarat.

Day 2 – Blue Carbon outreach and engagement with high school

On the second day, GO-BC delegates spent time visiting a local primary school in Bhuj where they conducted various STEM outreach activities aimed at highlighting the importance of local, coastal Blue Carbon ecosystems in the fight against climate change. During the visit, blue carbon experts and government representatives from the UK had some insightful discussions with school children and teachers surrounding how the local community interacts with, and values, coastal BC ecosystems in the area.

Day 3 – Blue Carbon science talks and discussions

The first workshop day at Ahmedabad University consisted of presentations and discussions from external and internal blue carbon experts from India, United Kingdom, Sri Lanka, and Indonesia. Topics included: mangrove mapping at global to national scales; the roles of mangroves in carbon sequestration, climate mitigation, and local livelihoods; mangrove restoration projects; and how coastal blue carbon ecosystems are included and integrated in national and global policy.

Day 4 – Blue Carbon priority science questions exercise

The final day was kicked off by early career researchers Alex Houston and Shrutika Parihar who presented their novel research on blue carbon ecosystems and research methods based on work from their Master's degrees and PhD's. Afterwards, a priority questions exercise was run by Bill Austin and Alex Houston, which brought together the views and opinions of all workshop participants to identify the 12 most pressing questions in the context of Blue Carbon science in India. These questions will directly contribute towards a collaborative publication aimed at developing a roadmap for incorporating Blue Carbon ecosystems into India's NDCs.

Workshop programme

Day 1

Session 1

- 09:00 Welcome to Ahmedabad University (Pankaj Chandra)
- 09:05 Welcome (Rebecca Berry)
- 09:10 Brief Opening Remarks
- 09:30 Round Table Introductions
- 10:00 The UN Ocean Decade Programme for Blue Carbon (Bill Austin)
- 10:20 Blue Carbon and the IPCC guidance (Hillary Kennedy)
- 10:40 Open Discussion

Session 2

- 11:30 The Global Mangroves Alliance (Tom Worthington)
- 11:50 Indonesia – a global blue carbon hotspot (Frida Sidik)
- 12:10 UK – integrating science and identifying blue carbon evidence gaps (DEFRA policy officials)
- 12:30 Open Discussion

Session 3

- 14:00 Mangrove restoration projects and the work of GUIDE (Vijay Kumar)
- 14:20 Blue carbon assessment in ecosystems (Dharmendra Shah)
- 14:40 Carbon sequestration potential of mangroves in Gujarat (C N Pandey)
- 15:00 Importance and role of Gujarat mangroves in climate change and livelihoods (Deepa Gaval)

Session 4

- 15:50 Blue carbon, sequestration and coastal sustainability (Rupesh Bhomia)
- 16:10 Open Discussion
- 16:30 Priority Questions Exercise – all workshop participants to discuss their experience and evidence needs (Bill Austin and Vijay Kumar)

Day 2

Session 1

09:00 Early Career Researcher talks and discussion (Shrutika Parihar, Alex Houston, and NCCR representative)

10:00 Priority Questions discussion and voting (All)

11:30 Priority Questions ranking and discussion (All)

Session 2

14:00 Priority Questions – writing subgroups (All)

16:00 Workshop Summary and Next Steps (Bill Austin and Vijay Kumar)

16:30 Close and Thanks

List of Abstracts

All abstracts are listed alphabetically according to surnames, and presented in the same order below.

1. The UN Ocean Decade Programme for Blue Carbon **(WA/GB)**
2. Blue carbon, sequestration and sustainability **(RB)**
3. Importance and role of Gujarat mangroves in climate change and livelihoods **(DG)**
4. Methodology for calculating OC stocks in surficial mangrove soils **(AH)**
5. Blue carbon and IPCC guidance **(HK)**
6. Mangrove restoration projects and the work of GUIDE **(VK)**
7. UK – integrating science and identifying blue carbon evidence gaps **(PO)**
8. Blue Carbon ecosystems: Ecosystem services and accounting **(UP)**
9. Carbon sequestration potential of mangroves in Gujarat **(CP)**
10. Blue Carbon sequestration of mangroves: Observed changes at Kachchh Region **(SP & MP)**
11. Blue carbon assessment in ecosystems **(DS & SK)**
12. Indonesia – a global blue carbon hotspot **(FS)**
13. The Global Mangroves Alliance **(TW)**

The United Nations Ocean Decade Programme for Blue Carbon in the Global Ocean (GO-BC): A brief introduction

William Austin (University of St Andrews, Scotland, UK)

The GO-BC programme contributes to the UN's Ocean Decade (2021-2030), delivering the “science we need for the ocean we want” and addressing global ocean challenges and supporting progress towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals through: research, collaboration, capacity building, and policy development. GO-BC codesigns and implements new blue carbon research to promote Nature-based Solutions for better ocean sustainability. Our expanding (already represented across 20 nations) Science Technical Working group shapes and guides the direction of new and emerging blue carbon research. Collaboration is at the heart of GO-BC, enhancing global to regional collaborative efforts by facilitating communication between stakeholders at all levels. Regional hubs act as focal points for collaborations across the globe. GO-BC also coordinates capacity building in blue carbon science across the globe, to build and enhance technical science capacity; for example, we have partnered with the International Atomic Energy Agency to deliver blue carbon training courses. GO-BC also strives to communicate scientific outputs to policy makers and communities clearly and effectively, to ensure that new blue carbon science is being utilised to its fullest extent.

Photo: GO-BC Science Technical Working group at the IAEA headquarters in Vienna, Austria.

Rupesh Bhomia (Centre for International Forestry Research (CIFOR), Sri Lanka)

Mangroves as a socio-ecological system are of paramount importance for combating climate change and ensuring sustainable coast and sustenance of coastal communities. Intact mangrove forests are tremendously important for climate change mitigation through the removal and storage of carbon in their biomass and soils. Mangroves also provide Indian coastal communities with food, fibre, fuel, protection from tsunamis and cyclones, and are essential to marine and coastal biodiversity. Despite numerous ecosystem services to society, these ecosystems are facing severe pressure from anthropogenic and natural causes.

Our ability to respond to such challenges and identify appropriate nature-based solutions is limited by lack of baseline information and scientific data on these vulnerable areas. Site appropriate restoration actions have greater probability of success when based on location specific ecological information, and following data driven adaptive management decision making. Therefore, an attempt to establish long-term monitoring plots to determine surface elevation changes in select mangrove regions along the Indian coast is underway. This program aims to provide information needed for management decision making, identifying restoration priorities, and planning interventions for mangrove conservation. This information will support India's efforts to enhance its climate ambition, report reductions in its forest carbon emissions, and more accurately account for carbon sequestration in its Nationally Determined Contributions.

The ongoing effort on ecological monitoring is undertaken in a total of 5 locations in India's east and west coast including mangroves of Andaman Islands, Sundarbans, Coringa, Bhitarkanika and Gulf of Kutch. This monitoring will establish total mangrove carbon stocks (forest inventory) using CIFOR protocols for the measurement, monitoring, and reporting of structure, biomass, and carbon stocks in mangrove forests (<https://www.cifor.org/knowledge/publication/3749>), Determine soil erosion and accretion rates by installing rod surface elevation table (rSET) at select locations (<https://www.usgs.gov/centers/eesc/science/surface-elevation-table>) and measure inundation frequency and salinity at select locations using automated data loggers.

Figure: 1. Map of monitoring sites in Coringa Wildlife Sanctuary; 2. Images from the field installing rSETs for sediment accretion and erosion data.

Deepa Gavali (Gujarat Ecology society, India)

Mangroves play a pivotal role in shoreline protection from erosion and storm surges in events of cyclones and tsunamis. In wake of climate change impact, Gujarat coastline especially Gulf of Kachchh is facing increase in cyclonic events. In the last five years, Gujarat coast has witnessed severe to very severe cyclonic storms events viz., Vayu (2019), Tuktutae (2021) and Biparjoy (2023). The presence of mangroves along the Gulf of Kachchh played crucial role acting as natural bio shield protecting the coastline from high waves and damages to property and human life. Presence of mangroves becomes important in wake of population growth of 77% along the Gujarat coastline from 1991 to 2011. Additionally rapid urbanisation of 43 coastal villages in Gulf of Khambhat region, 19 villages in South Gujarat Coast and 5 villages in Gulf of Kachchh region is exposing the populace to threats arising from climate change. Thus, mangrove conservation and restoration is an important tool to combat climate change and build resilience.

The mangrove area also supports shrimps, mud skipper, crabs and snails, which is the source of livelihood of the pagadiya fishermen present across the Gujarat coastline. The seeds of *Avicennia* spp. is used by the coastal community as source of food and consumed after cooking properly during the lean period when fishing is banned. The mangrove associates like *Sueada*, *Portulaca* are consumed as vegetables by the locals. Mangrove leaves are used as fodder for camel, goat and sheep and is the major source of fodder during the drought years. With the unpredicted rainfall and alteration in cropping pattern, mangrove habitat support livelihood opportunity for the coastal communities. Hence, there is urgent need to align the traditional knowledge with the mangrove conservation and restoration, which can form an important tool to combat climate change and build resilience.

Soil Incubations as a Viable Method for Measuring Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Blue Carbon Ecosystems

Alex Houston (University of St Andrews, Scotland, UK)

The protection and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems (BCEs; saltmarshes, seagrasses, mangroves) may contribute to net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions abatement and help address the global challenge of mitigating and adapting to climate change. BCEs have attracted particular interest in international policy frameworks and private market schemes due to their effective storage of organic carbon in their soils, and historic and ongoing habitat degradation and losses which have created large-scale opportunities for their protection and restoration. To constrain the climate abatement service of BCEs, an improved understanding of both the rate and drivers of GHG emissions from these systems is required (Macreadie et al., 2019). High spatial and temporal variability of GHG emissions makes field sampling complex and can be a barrier to data collection. Laboratory incubations can be a more accessible alternative for measuring GHG fluxes in controlled conditions and assessing drivers of decomposition in BCE soils. Using a methodology for short-term laboratory incubation studies developed for saltmarsh soils as an example (Houston et al., 2024), we will discuss the potential suitability of laboratory incubation studies for understanding rates and drivers of GHG emissions from BCEs in India.

Photo: Alex Houston presenting his PhD research.

Hillary Kennedy (University of Bangor, Wales, UK)

Mangroves, saltmarsh and seagrass meadows, termed Blue Carbon Ecosystems (BCE) are globally distributed and known for their high organic carbon (OC) accumulation rates and large and persistent soil OC stocks. Quantification of these attributes on a global scale led to the development of international policy which allows countries to include BCE in their climate mitigation policies, through their Greenhouse Gas Inventories (GHGI). Chapter 4 of the 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHGI: Wetlands, provides guidance to account for GHG emissions and removals due to anthropogenic activities related to BCE loss or restoration. The guidance provides methodology to estimate the effects of BCE management at different levels of complexity. Tier 1 represents a simple first order approach for countries lacking national data by providing default emission values, based on globally available data, for each management activity and BCE. Since the coinage of the term Blue Carbon and the adoption of the Wetland Supplement there has been a strong and continued acceleration in the evidence base and understanding of the role that BCE play in climate mitigation. However, there have been few countries that have included coastal wetlands in their national GHGI. Those that have (USA, Australia, UAE), have used nationally available data to provide country specific (Tier 2) emission factors. India has long experience in mangrove restoration and is financing projects such as “Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Incomes”, where mangrove plantations along the coastline and on salt pans are being planted. India is also committed to achieving additional forest and tree cover through its Nationally Determined Contributions. Through these activities and further measurement of stock changes and fluxes India will be well placed to account for its national emissions and removals in coastal wetlands.

Photo: Mangrove replanting as part of a mangrove restoration project in Kachch region, Gujarat.

Mangrove Initiatives at the Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology (GUIDE)

Vijay Kumar (Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology, India)

Dr. V. Vijay Kumar, Director, Gujarat Institute of Desert Ecology (GUIDE), Bhuj-Kachchh Gujarat State has the 2nd largest mangrove cover (1177 km²) in the country (4975 km²). In which 169 km² falls under moderately dense (14%) category while other areas are covered by sparse mangroves. The state encompasses two gulfs, Gulf of Kachchh and Gulf of Khambhat.

The Gulf of Kachchh, the Kachchh coast supports 794.77 km² (67.5%) and 234 km² mangrove areas (19.88%) are distributed along the Jamnagar, Dwarka coastal areas. Etc. (19.88%). Remaining mangroves are distributed along the Saurashtra coast (Amreli, Junagadh, Gir- Somnath), i.e., 5.7 km² (0.48%) and Gulf of Khambhat (Bhavnagar, Ahmedabad, Anand, Bharuch, Surat, Navsari and Valsad districts) support 139.77 km² (11.87%) area under mangroves.

GUIDE has undertaken mangrove plantation along the Kachchh coast covering more than 500ha and monitoring over 20,000ha mangrove plantations undertaken by various departments, industries and ports in many parts of Gujarat. The presentation also covered the scenario of drylands and climate change issues along with major challenges in plantation and management of mangroves in the Gujarat state. Kachchh coastal area is dominated by *Avicenia marina*. Therefore, GUIDE along with Adani Foundation, Mundra has initiated a multispecies Mangrove Biodiversity Park by adding species such as *R. mucronate*, *C. tagal*, etc. following zonation techniques since the salinity of the sea water in the area is around 38 ppt. Apart from these, GUIDE has taken initiatives in seaweed cultivation at Simmer and Jamnagar coastal areas.

Photo: GO-BC experts, led by Dr. Vijay Kumar from GUIDE, visit mangroves in Kachchh, Gujarat.

Sustainable Management of the Coringa Mangrove Ecosystem: An Ecosystem Services Perspective

Uma Sankar Panda (National Centre for Coastal Research, India)

The blue carbon ecosystem in India sequesters approximately 2% of the India's annual carbon emissions, equivalent to 702.42 million tonnes of CO₂e. Preservation of mangrove cover has the potential to sequester an additional 207.91 million tonnes of CO₂e. Coringa, the second-largest mangrove ecosystem, spans approximately 135 km² within Coringa Wildlife Sanctuary (CWLS), providing various ecosystem services crucial for the local community's livelihoods. The ecosystem is rich in biodiversity with more than 40 ecosystem services with 16 mangrove tree species, 137 phytoplankton, 81 zooplankton, 126 microbenthos, 37 meiobenthos, and 114 macrobenthos. Restoration efforts initiated since the early 1990s, involving governmental, NGO, and community collaboration, have led to increased land cover and biomass of mangrove forests. However, the eastern boundary of the Coringa mangrove faces degradation at the sea interface due to sedimentation and various stressors, resulting in the loss of 7.4 km² of mangrove. In-situ data on sediment, water, and biological parameters corroborated with satellite images reveals the spatio-temporal changes of the ecosystem services with respect to climate change and anthropogenic pressures. Despite challenges such as pollution, industrialization, overexploitation, and disease outbreaks impacting the Coringa fishery, successful management through community-government partnerships has been achieved. Eco-tourism activities initiated by the local government have provided economic benefits, further enhancing community involvement in mangrove conservation. This collaborative model in Coringa can serve as a blueprint for sustainable development initiatives. The National Centre for Coastal Research is employing a comprehensive scientific approach to assess ecosystem services and climate impacts, facilitating the sustainable management of this unique blue carbon ecosystem.

Policy Officials (Department for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs, UK)

Climate change combined with other pressures such as pollution and over exploitation is having a catastrophic impact on ocean health. In response, the UK aims to mitigate emissions, support adaptation, and build resilience of species and habitats. Key policy drivers include international commitments, the 25-year environment plan, the Fisheries Act, the Marine Strategy Regulations 2010, and the UK Climate Change Act.

The UK is responding to marine climate change risks and is supporting adaptation through the National Adaptation Programme (NAP). The NAP identifies five marine risks and outlines actions needed including: data gathering, improved understanding and management of anthropogenic pressures. Various UK marine sectors are contributing to mitigating climate change and contributing towards Net Zero. This includes fishing sector emissions reductions and offshore wind energy production. Additionally, blue carbon habitats are recognised for their role in mitigating and adapting to climate change. Current evidence shows that blue carbon habitats in the UK offer efficient carbon removal and storage potential, alongside biodiversity and adaptation benefits.

The UK Blue Carbon Evidence Partnership (UKBCEP), announced at COP26, brings together science and policy experts from across the UK and aims to coordinate blue carbon research. The UKBCEP has identified shared objectives, including potential inclusion of saltmarsh and seagrass blue carbon habitats into the UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory, encouraging investment in blue carbon habitats, reducing impacts of human and environmental pressures, and managing habitats on a seascape scale.

Key evidence needs identified by the UKBCEP include standardised methods and quality control, habitat mapping, carbon stock data, understanding impacts of human activities and climate change, and socio-economic benefits and costs, where: standardised methods will increase collaboration and data accuracy; habitat mapping provides baseline information for accounting, biodiversity monitoring, and management decisions; and improved understanding of carbon stock and emissions will enable more accurate greenhouse gas emissions reporting.

Overall, collaboration among Governments, eNGOs and academia is essential to further our evidence base and enable an understanding of blue carbon habitats' role in mitigating and adapting to climate change.

Integrating mangrove conservation as part of India's climate policies

Shrutika Parihar and **Minal Pathak** (Ahmedabad University, India)

Nature-based solutions like blue carbon ecosystems (BCEs), e.g., mangroves, salt marsh, coastal wetlands, and seagrasses, would be able to play crucial roles in carbon sequestration supporting India's commitment to achieving net zero emissions by 2070. India has the highest mangrove cover in in BCEs, with 4992 km² (FSI, 2021), salt marsh 290-1698 km² (Akhand et al., 2023), seagrass 517 km² and coastal wetland 5,621 km² (NCSCM, 2018). The estimated carbon sequestration potential is 702 MT CO₂e, equivalent to 22% of India's annual carbon emissions (Ref). Mangrove restoration and conservation can contribute to an additional 208 MT CO₂e (ORF, 2022). India's current "Long-Term Low Carbon Development Strategy (LT-LEDS)" submitted to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) does not explicitly focus on blue carbon.

India has committed to create an additional carbon sink of 2.5 to 3 billion tonnes of CO₂eq through additional forest and tree cover by 2030. The goal would be partly achieved by creating 540 sq km of carbon sinks and planting mangroves across the country's coastal areas under the Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats & Tangible Incomes (MISHTI) scheme. India's current NDC goals and aligned policies do not adequately address the terrestrial (Life on land) and marine ecosystems (Life below water) for several reasons. Reasons include a lack of temporal data, limited technical skills for conducting field measurements, challenges in calculating carbon stock, and difficulties interpreting satellite imagery. There is lack of clarity on the restoration measures for blue carbon and information on the restoration success rate. Additionally, high costs are associated with monitoring and verification to such remote coastal sites due to poor accessibility. This study assesses the state of mangrove inclusion in India's climate policies and plans and identifies measures to enhance terrestrial and marine ecosystems under national policies to better leverage the potential of blue carbon for achieving simultaneous benefits of climate change mitigation and adaptation and sustainable development.

Photo: Shrutika Parihar presenting her research.

Blue carbon assessment in ecosystems other than mangroves: Needs in the Indian Scenario

Dharmendra Shah and **Shreestuti Khare** (Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, India)

While several different kinds of ecosystems are located in coastal and marine areas, it is the mangroves, tidal marshes, seagrass ecosystems have received major attention from researchers globally. In the Indian scenario, mangrove ecosystems have received the most attention and data on several aspects which can contribute to fair blue carbon stock and flux estimation exist. This is not the case for other blue carbon ecosystems like salt marshes, sea grasses, marine benthic algae and other ecosystems.

Tropical salt marshes have a different structure and diversity from temperate salt marshes. When associated with mangroves they are generally found on the landward margin on soils with higher salinity levels than mangroves. Their species richness is fairly well known through several studies at sites across the vast Indian coastline. There is, however, a huge difference in the national estimates of spatial extent by different groups of researchers at the national level with one study estimating about 250 km² while another putting the figure at more than 850 km². Our study in an area covering just 500 km of the 6700 km long coastline of India estimates the salt marsh area to be 210 km². Studies on the blue carbon stocks are also restricted to a few sites and a few species. Arriving at fair national estimates of blue carbon stocks and fluxes for the salt marsh ecosystem in India would hence be difficult and error prone.

The areal extent and the species richness of seagrass ecosystems has been the subject of several studies across widespread sites along the Indian coastline. Carbon stocks have been estimated for three sites in different studies. Their growth also varies from the highly turbid water in Gujarat in west India to almost clear waters in the Andaman & Nicobar Islands. The existing information would be insufficient to estimate national stocks which would need more site-specific and multi-temporal studies to factor in seasonal variation.

A few recent studies have pointed to the role of benthic marine algae ecosystem as a source of allochthonous carbon to other blue carbon ecosystems like seagrasses. Globally as well as in India this ecosystem has received little attention. With its expansive mudflats coupled with estimates from a few studies, the areal extent of this ecosystem in India is expected to be similar to salt marshes. Data on carbon stocks is also non-existent.

Frida Sidik (Research Centre for Oceanography, National Agency for Research and Innovation, Indonesia)

Indonesia is a blue carbon rich country, consisting about 3.3 million hectares of mangrove forests and over 300,000 hectares of seagrass meadows. It is estimated that Indonesia's blue carbon ecosystems account for 17% of global blue carbon reservoir (Alongi et al, 2015). Despite their importance, a decline in mangrove and seagrass area in Indonesia still occurs caused by anthropogenic activities and natural disasters. In response to coastal ecosystems degradation, the Government of Indonesia has set up several measures to protect and restore coastal ecosystems that correspond to 'blue carbon' policy. For example, the Government has set ambitious targets of 600,000 hectares mangrove rehabilitation in 2024 and MPA establishment within 30% of Indonesia waters in 2045. In terms of international commitments, Indonesia has increased emission reduction targets to 31.89% unconditionally and 43.20% conditionally in Enhanced NDC. This effort opens the opportunity for Indonesia's blue carbon ecosystems to play significant role in climate mitigation actions.

The recognition of coastal ecosystem's importance in climate change mitigation has emerged in Indonesia since blue carbon was firstly introduced in 2010. The early recognition was marked by the establishment of blue carbon science group at the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, which is then scaled up to policy development. The Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries has been mandated as the key 'blue carbon' agency in Indonesia and works with the Ministry of Environment and Forestry in governing blue carbon ecosystems as a solution to tackle climate change. To date, blue carbon has been prepared into financing system and considered to be included in carbon market in Indonesia.

To support the Government in mainstreaming blue carbon into policy and carbon market readiness, the research agenda has been set to address challenges, gaps, and opportunities in mangrove and seagrass blue carbon. The research activities cover the assessment of blue carbon stock, sequestration and emissions, the assessment of habitat extent for blue carbon ecosystems inventory and the development restoration methods that can result in best practices for achieving blue carbon potentials and sustainable livelihood. In addition to research activities, a series of capacity building activities have been conducted for government officials, academics, coastal managers and practitioners and local communities to establish blue carbon knowledge among them and increase their awareness in blue carbon ecosystems.

Overview of the Global Mangrove Alliance

Tom Worthington (University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)

We are in a golden-age of open-data and technological advancement, which is allowing researchers to examine changes in coastal ecosystems over-longer time periods, at finer resolutions and with greater accuracy. Despite the wealth of information being produced the challenge remains in translating this science to on the ground action. It is critical that data that can support science-based conservation and restoration is easily and freely accessible to aid the management of coastal ecosystems. Among the coastal ecosystems, mangroves have the most developed networks of actors. For example, the Global Mangrove Alliance (GMA) is a collaboration of NGOs, governments, scientists, industry, local communities, and funders working towards a common goal of conserving and restoring mangrove ecosystems.

In 2022, the GMA published their new goals: halting mangrove loss due to human actions, restoring half of recent losses and doubling long-term secure protection. These targets are underpinned by the latest research, with the data that supports them made accessible through the Global Mangrove Watch platform. The platform seeks to emulate the success of other data-sharing and advocacy platforms such as the Global Forest Watch and Global Fishing Watch. The Global Mangrove Watch platform contains the latest global scale mangrove research including data on mangrove extent and change, ecosystem service values and restoration potential. This information is supported by publications such as the State of the World's Mangroves aimed at communicating the latest research, and the Best Practice Guidelines for Mangrove Restoration designed to support science-based restoration.

Photo: A warm welcome by school children during the school visit in Bhuj.

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